

Stability Analysis for Seed Yield of Linseed (*Linum Usitatissimum*) Genotype in Saline Affected Soils of South-Western Coastal Region of Bangladesh

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Abstract

A vast area of cultivable lands in saline affected coastal region of South-Western Bangladesh remains fallow during Rabi (winter) season due to non-availability of saline tolerant crop species or varieties. Linseed (*Linum usitatissimum*) is known as a medium salt tolerant crop with diverse uses. The crop may be a good choice to utilize these saline prone lands. For this purpose a salt tolerant high yielding variety is essential. With this view in mind, a multi-environmental trial of ten linseed genotypes was conducted in saline soils of four locations in this coastal region during Rabi (winter) season of 2020-21, 2021-22 and 2022-23 to identify superior genotypes based on their yield performance, stability and adaptability.

The AMMI model ANOVA revealed that the main effects of genotypes (G), environment (E) and GE interaction effects explain 83.95, 1.07 and 12.02% of seed yield variation, respectively. The GE interaction was further subdivided into 9 IPCAs of which first 6 were significant, and the first two IPCAs explained 82.3% of total sum of square where IPCA 1 explained 67.60% and IPCA 2 14.70%. Mean comparison showed that mean seed yield of ten genotypes varied from 625 to 1345 kg ha⁻¹ and that of 12 environments varied from 937-1050 kg h⁻¹ with a grand mean of 1000 kg ha⁻¹. AMMI 1, AMMI 2 and GGE biplot analyses depicted that the highest yielder genotype was G2 followed by G6, G1 and G4. The lowest yielding genotype was G9 followed by G10, G5 and G3. The most stable genotype was G2 followed by G7, G9, G1 and G4, which were widely accepted to almost all environments. The ASV, EV, CV, SIPC and yield index analyses revealed that genotypes G2, G4 and G6 were found to be superior genotypes in seed yield and consistently demonstrating high mean performance across tested environments. Considering the results of biplot analyses and stability parameters like ASV, SIPC, CV, and EV, genotypes G1, G2, G4 and G6 were identified as superior genotypes. The genotypes, G6 exhibited high seed yield, wide adaptation and excellent stable performance over all four tested locations.

Thus BD-10698 (G6) can be selected as a variety for cultivation in the saline affected soils of South-Western coastal region of Bangladesh. Genotypes BD-10708 (G2) and Lin-1403 (G4) showed excellent yield performance but medium stability, while Lin-1203 (G9) showed excellent stability but low yield performance. So, BD-10708, Lin-1403 and Lin-1203 can be utilized to develop salt tolerant linseed variety through required breeding program.

Keywords: *Linseed, genotype, stability, adaptability, saline soil.*

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Introduction

Linseed or flax (*Linum usitatissimum* L.) belongs to the family Linaceae is an oldest crop with diverse uses. Generally, it is cultivated for the purposes of oil and fiber. Its seeds are used to extract oil and culms are used to extract fiber after retting. It is a source of food, feed, fiber, oil, medicine, and industrial raw material. Linseed possesses very healthy fatty acids (linoleic-Omega 6 and alpha-linolenic acids or Omega 3). Consumption of its seeds is beneficial to human health and recommended for treatment of cardiac diseases. Linseed oil contains high quantity of alpha-linolenic acid (ALA), which gives the oil quick drying properties, and is used for manufacturing paints and varnishes, oilcloths and other similar products. Linseed oilcake remaining after extraction of oil is very rich in micronutrients, proteins, vitamins and dietary cellulose. The oilcake is used as a valuable ingredient of feed for the livestock, poultry and fast growing animals (Singh et al. 2011, Dubey et al. 2020).

An area is known as saline when its soil contains an excess of soluble salts especially sodium sulphate and sodium chloride. The dominant salt is sodium chloride (Munns & Tester, 2008). In Bangladesh, about 1.06 million hectares of lands in 19 districts are affected by salinity in the coastal and offshore regions lies around the northern apex of the Bay of Bengal. In South-Western Bangladesh, saline affected soils are found in the districts of Barisal, Barguna and Patuakhali. The pH of the saturated saline soil is usually less than 8.3. The soils are slightly moderately saline on the surface but highly saline in sub-surface layers. The salinity is reduced during rainy season but increases in dry season. During rainy season the dominant crop of the areas is *Amon* rice. After harvest of rice, the lands remain fallow in *Rabi* (winter) season due to lack of saline tolerant crops or varieties (Ahsan, 2010) Banglapedia 2014 & Rasel et al. 2013).

Linseed is a moderately salt tolerant crop (Day et al. 2018). It may be grown in the saline prone zones of Bangladesh. For this purpose a stable, high yielding and salt tolerant linseed variety is necessary. Selection of salt tolerance genotypes is an effective approach for varietal development of a crop. Generally, breeders grow genotypes in saline affected soil and select better performers on the basis of their physiological, morphological and yield responses (Kaya et al. 2019).

The genotypes of a crop grown in different environments are frequently encountered significant fluctuations in yield performance, especially when the growing environments are distinctly different, the test genotypes respond differentially to the changes in the growing environments. Environmental conditions play a significant role in the variation of agricultural traits in linseed and the performance of the crop is strongly influenced by environmental factors (Adane & Ararsa 2018 and Amsalu, 2020). Therefore, studying the stability of linseed genotypes to identify a suitable variety is essential for maximizing yield potential for the saline affected regions (Tadesse et al. 2017 and Yadav et al, 2020).

The fluctuation of a crop performance with changing environments is technically termed as genotype x environment interaction (GEI). The GEI is a universal phenomenon when different genotypes are tested in a number of environments and is an important issue for plant breeders and agronomists to predict variety behavior in different locations across different years prior to any varietal recommendation. Usually, environment expresses the most of the total yield variations, while genotype and genotype x environment interaction are less effective (Yan and Kang 2003, Dehghani et al. 2008 and Aboye 2021). Understanding the GEI and stability analysis can help plant breeders to select stable genotypes.

The yield performance of a crop is a combined result of the genotype, environment and interaction between genotype and environment. The GE interaction directs the identification of the most stable genotypes which are suitable for specific environment, and/or genotypes with a general adaptability and is suitable for several test environments (Mohammadi, 2002). To evaluate the consistency of linseed seed yield and to develop genotypes that respond optimally and consistently across years and geographic regions, it is necessary to research on yield stability and GE interactions. The main objectives of the present study were to identify high-yielding, widely or specifically adapted, stable and salt tolerant linseed genotypes suitable to grow in the South-Western Coastal saline areas of Bangladesh.

Material and Methods

Experimental Materials, Locations and Duration

Ten linseed genotypes were tested in this present multi-environmental trial namely Neela, BD-10708, BD-10707, Lin-1403, Lin-2403, BD-10698, Lin-S-19, Lin-1503/2, Lin-1203 and Lin-W-17 (Table 1). The genotypes were obtained from the Genetic Resource Center of Bangladesh Agricultural Research Institute (BARI), Gazipur, Bangladesh. Neela is a nationally released variety and was included in the experiment as a standard material.

The materials were tested at two locations of Amtali Upazila under Barguna district and at another two locations of Kalapara Upazila under Patuakhali district). The locations of the experiment are representative of saline soils in the South-West Coastal region under AEZ-13 of Bangladesh. The experiment was conducted in three consecutive *Rabi* (winter) season (December to April) of 2020-21, 2021-22 and 2022-23. Each year and every location was considered as a separate environment, constituting altogether 12 test environments as described in Table 2.

Experimental, Design, Layout and Data Collection

In all locations and seasons, the experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with 3 replications. Each replication was represented by a 4 m x 1 m plot planted with two rows of each genotype. Row to row distance was 40 cm and plant to plant distance was 10 cm. Space between plots was 50 cm. The recommended production package was followed to raise a good crop. Total number of plants in a plot was harvested at fully matured stage. The harvested plants were dried in the sun and seed were separated from the branches by manual threshing. Seeds were sun dried and plot wise yield were recorded. The seed yield was expressed as kilogram per hectare (kg ha^{-1}).

Table 1. Descriptions of Tested Environments during *Rabi* (December to April) Seasons of 2020-2023

Linseed genotypes				Environments (Location & Yeas)			
Code	Name	Code	Name	Code	Name	Code	name
G1	Neela	G6	BD-10698	E1	Uttar Kalayanpur 2020-21	E7	Diarankhola 2020-21
G2	BD-10708	G7	Lin-S-19	E2	Uttar Kalayanpur 2021-22	E8	Diarankhola 2021-22

G3	BD-10707	G8	Lin-1503/2	E3	Uttar Kalayanpur 2022-23	E9	Diaramkhola 2022-23
G4	Lin-1403	G9	Lin-1203	E4	Dakkhin Kalayanpur 2020-21	E10	Nayapara 2020-21
G5	Lin-2403	G10	Lin-W-17	E5	Dakkhin Kalayanpur 2021-22	E11	Nayapara 2021-22
				E6	Dakkhin Kalayanpur 2022-23	E12	Nayapara 2022-23

Table 2. Geographic Position, Temperature, Rainfall, and Soil pH and Soil Salinity of Four Experimental Locations

Description of location	Upzila: Amtali, District : Barguna		Upzila : Kalapara, District : Patuakhali	
Latitude	22.129 °N		21.986 °N	
Longitude	90.229 °E		90.242 °E	
Altitude	1.9 m		3.5 m	
	During cropping period (December-April)			
	Uttar Kalayanpur	Dokkhin Kalayanpur	Diaramkhola	Nayapara
Temperature (Min-Max)	15.4- 31.1°C	15.4- 31.1°C	18.3-29.5 °C	18.3-29.5 °C
Rainfall	13.47 mm	13.47 mm	14.36 mm	14.36 mm
Rainy days	2.03 days	2.03 days	3.34 days	3.34 days
Soil pH (0-10 cm deep)	5.7-6.9	6.0-7.1	35.7-6.8	5.7-7.0
Salinity (0-10 cm deep)	3.8-11.9 dS m ⁻¹	9.0-15.4 dS m ⁻¹	8.0-14.8 dS m ⁻¹	8.5-15.3 dSm ⁻¹

Statistical Analysis of Data

Combined Analysis of Variance: The data on seed yield of 10 genotypes across 12 test environments were analyzed through combined analysis of variance according to Gomez & Gomez (1983) to determine the effects of genotypes (G), environments (E), and GE interactions effects.

AMMI analysis: The additive main effect and multiplicative interaction (AMMI) model, which combines standard ANOVA with principal components (PC) analysis (Zobel et al. 1988) was performed using the model suggested by Crossa et al. (1991) and used by Tadesse et al. (2017). Standard ANOVA explained the additive main effects of genotype and environments, while PCA revealed non-additive portion.

AMMI Biplot analysis

Different biplots were used to show a clear understanding about specific GEI combination and the general pattern of adaptation and relationship among the environments.

AMMI 1 Biplot: The main effect of seed yield was placed on X-axis and the first AMMI principal component axis (IPCA1) on Y-axis to create AMMI1 biplot, which facilitated successful selection of genotypes with high yield and stability from the tested genotypes.

AMMI 2 Biplot: The first principal component axes (IPCA1) was placed on X-axis and the IPCA2 on Y-axis to create AMMI 2 biplot as suggested by Yan (2002) and Yan & Tinker (2005).

GGE Biplot Analysis: The GGE stands for genotype main effect (G) plus the genotype-by-environment interaction (GE), which are the two sources of variation of site regression (SREG) model. In GGE biplot analysis, genotype main effects and genotype-by-environment interactions (GE) are combined into GGE, emphasizing their joint importance in evaluating genotypes, particularly when GE interaction is repeatable (Yan et al. 2007).

Relationships among test environments: Another GGE biplot plot was created using PCA1 & PCA2 scores of 12 enrolments on X-axis and Y-axis respectively to depict relationship among the genotypes (Adane & Ararsa 2018).

Stability analysis: Six stability parameters were computed and used to rank the genotypes following the suggestions as suggested by Aboye (2021). These were AMMI Stability Value (ASV) (Purchase et al 2000), sum of IPCs scores (SIPC) (Sneller et al. 1997), yield stability index (YSI) (Farshadfar 2008), eigenvalue stability parameters (EV) & coefficient of variation (CV) (Aboye 2021), and WAASB (Memon et al. 2023).

Y x WAASB biplot: Y x WAASB biplot was created by placing mean seed yield on the X-axis and WAASB value on Y-axis. The biplot separated the genotypes into four quadrants, facilitating selection of genotypes with high seed yield and stability from tested genotypes.

Statistical packages

Combined ANOVA, AMMI analysis, Biplot analysis, ASV, YSI, GGE biplots and MTSI were calculated using R-Studio, R version 4.0.3 by using ‘agricolae’ and ‘metan’ R packages.

Results and Discussion

Combined Analysis of Variance and Performance of Genotypes

The results of combined analysis of variance revealed highly significant ($P \leq 0.001$) differences in genotypes, environments, and Genotypes x environment interaction (Table 3). Mean comparison of the tested genotypes revealed that seed yield varied with genotypes and environments. The seed yield of 10 genotypes across 12 environments (120 treatment combinations) ranged from the minimum of 602 kg ha⁻¹ in Lin-1203 at Uttar Kalayanpur in 2022-23 and Nayapara in 2021-22 to the maximum of 1467 kg ha⁻¹ at Diaramkhola in 2022-23 with a grand mean of 1000 kg ha⁻¹. The pooled mean of seed yield of 10 genotypes over 12 environments ranged from the lowest of 625 kg ha⁻¹ to the highest of 1345 kg ha⁻¹. The maximum pooled mean of seed yield was obtained from BD-10708 followed by BD-10698 (1285 kg ha⁻¹), Lin-1403 (1151 kg ha⁻¹) and Neela (1149 kg ha⁻¹), while the lowest from Lin-1203 followed by Lin-W-17 (786 kg ha⁻¹) and Lin-2403 (BD-10707). The pooled mean of seed yield of all 12 environments over 10 genotypes ranged 937 to 1050 kg ha⁻¹. The highest pooled mean was found at Diaramkhola in 2022-23 and the lowest from the same location in 2021-22 (Table 4, Figs. 1 & 2). Variations in seed yield of genotypes with genotypes and environments have also been reported by other investigators (Tadesse et al. 2017, Adane & Arasa 2018 and Aboye 2021).

AMMI Analysis

Results of AMMI Model analysis of variance for seed yield revealed that main effects of genotypes and environments, and interaction effects of genotype-by-environment (GEI) were highly significant and explained respectively 83.95, 1.07 and 12.02% of the total sum of squares (Table 3). The interaction effects between genotypes and environments demonstrated that genotypes responded differently to the variation in environmental conditions, and genotypes may be selected for adaption to specific environments as suggested by various investigators (Farshadfar & Sutka 2003, 2006, Jacobsz et al. 2015, Tadesse 2017, Adane & Ararsa 2018 and, Amasalu 2020).

Table 3. AMMI Analysis of Variance for Seed Yield (kg h⁻¹) of Ten Linseed Genotypes Across 12 Environments in a Saline Zone of Bangladesh

Source of variation	DF	Sum of Square	Mean Square	% Explained of SS
Environment (E)	11	363066.80	33006.07**	1.70
Replication (Environment)	24	36820.31	1534.18ns	0.17

Genotype (Gen)	9	17890763.00	1987863.0**	83.95	
Env*Gen	99	2561026.00	25868.95**	12.02	
					Cumulative
	IPCA1	19	1730125.00	91059.19**	67.60
	IPCA2	17	377159.10	22185.83**	14.70
	IPCA3	15	232128.70	15475.25**	9.10
	IPCA4	13	112814.70	8678.051**	4.40
	IPCA5	11	52742.16	4794.74*	2.10
	IPCA6	9	47599.04	5288.78*	1.90
	IPCAA7	7	8226.76	1175.25ns	0.30
	IPCA8	5	201.11	40.22ns	0.00
	IPCA9	3	30.12	10.04ns	0.00
Residuals		216	459187.30	2125.88	
Total		359	21310863.41		

*. Significant at 5%, **.Significant at 1%, ns. Not significant.

Table 4. Mean Seed Yield of 10 Linseed Genotypes Evaluated across 12 Environments

	Genotype	Uttar Kalayanpur			Dakkhin Kalayanpur			Diaramkhola			Nayapara			Pooled Mean
		2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	2020-21	2021-22	2022-23	
		E1	E2	E3	E4	E5	E6	E7	E8	E9	E10	E11	E12	
G1	Neela (G1)	1247	988	1134	1325	1250	1090	1156	1060	1173	1095	1134	1132	1149
G2	BD-10708	1422	1292	1358	1048	1426	1324	1425	1307	1467	1331	1358	1387	1345
G3	BD-10707	984	836	830	1037	812	856	886	731	834	814	830	784	853
G4	Lin-1403	1160	1140	1058	1036	1163	1168	1245	1143	1258	1166	1058	1218	1151
G5	Lin-2403	897	760	982	1227	725	700	707	649	749	885	982	697	830
G6	BD-10698	1335	1216	1286	1277	1338	1246	1335	1225	1342	1237	1286	1302	1285
G7	Lin-S-19	1072	1064	1210	1063	1075	1012	1066	978	1088	955	1210	1047	1070
G8	Lin-1503/2	722	912	906	745	988	934	976	895	1003	1025	906	867	907
G9	Lin-1203	633	608	602	656	637	622	617	566	665	673	602	612	625
G10	Lin-W-17	809	684	678	681	900	778	796	813	919	744	678	952	786
	Minimum	633	608	602	656	637	622	617	566	665	673	602	612	624
	Maximum	1422	1292	1358	1325	1426	1324	1425	1307	1467	1331	1358	1387	1345
	Mean	1028	950	1004	1010	1031	973	1021	937	1050	993	1004	1000	1000

LSD (P≤0.05): Genotype =77.01, Environment=26.68, Genotype x Environment = 84.35. Abbreviations: E1=Uttar Kalayanpur 2020-21, E2= Uttar Kalayanpur 2021-22, E3= Uttar Kalayanpur 2022-23, E4= Dakkhin Kalayanpur 2020-21, E5= Dakkhin Kalayanpur 2021-22, E6= Dakkhin Kalayanpur 2023-24, E7= Diaramkhola 2020-21, E8= Diaramkhola 2021-22, E9= Diaramkhola 2022-23, E10= Nayapara 2020-21, E11= Nayapara 2021-22, E12= Nayapara 2022-23

The significant GEI with 12.02% variance was further subdivided into 9 interactive principal components (IPCA). The IPCA1 to IPCA4 was highly significant (P≤0.001) and that of IPCA5 & IPCA6 were significant (P≤0.05). The IPCA1 & IPCA2 explained 67.60% and 14.70% of the variability relating to GEI with a degree of freedoms of 19 and 17, respectively. The IPCA3 and PCA4 accounted for 9.19%

and 4.40% of the variability with a degree of freedom of 15 and 13, respectively. The IPCA5 & IPCA6 explained 2.10 and 1.90 of variability of SS with degree of a freedom of 9 and 7, respectively. The first seven IPCAs together accounted for 100.00% variability of GE interaction SS (Table 3). Findings of the present investigation revealed that the extracted IPCAs are capable of providing adequate information on the interaction effects but their degree decreased from the first to the last IPCAs. The findings are in agreement with the reports of Yadavi et al. (2014), Tadesse et al. (2017), Adane & Ararsa (2018) and Amasalu (2020).

AMMI Biplot Analysis

In the present investigation, four different biplots were created to show the potential of genotypes with high seed yield, their correlation with the environments under study and stability of genotypes under evaluation.

AMMI 1 Biplot

Results of AMMI ANOVA (Table 3) revealed that the IPCA I axis accounted the majority of the variance (67.60%). Following the suggestions of Ebdon & Gauch (2002), the AMMI I biplot was created by presenting the mean seed yield of 10 genotypes across 12 environments and that of 12 environments over 10 genotypes on the X-axis, known as main effects, and IPCAI scores of both factors on the Y-axis, which represents multiplicative effects (Fig. 1). Genotypes or environments placed in the right side of mean yield line indicate high yielders and those in the left side indicate low yielders. Genotypes with low IPCA scores close to zero are more stable and large IPCA scores indicate least stable genotypes (Ebdon & Gauch 2002).

Figure 1. AMMI 1 Biplot Analysis of the First Interaction Principal Component Axis (IPCA 1) Versus Seed Yield (kg ha^{-1}) of 10 Genotypes across 12 Environments

Note: Abbreviation as in Table 1

Accordingly, the biplot depicted that E10, E2 & E6 placed near the origin of the biplot with the shorter vectors suggesting the least changeable environment (changeable), while E4 had longer vector from the origin indicated highly interactive environment. E9, E5, E1 and E7 placed in the right side of the mean seed yield line indicating the most favorable environments for higher seed yield. On the other hand, E8, E6 and E2 placed in left side of the grand mean line depicting poor environments for seed yield. Environments E3, E4, E10, E12 and E12 located on or close to the mean yield line indicating seed yield almost at par with the grand mean. In right side of the mean yield line, the furthest genotype was G2 indicating the highest seed yielder followed by G6, G1, G4 and G7. The lowest yielding genotype was G9 followed by G10, G5 and G3, which were positioned in the left side of mean line and produced seed below the overall mean. G6 was found to be the least interactive genotype with the environments because it was positioned near the IPCAI line in AMMI I biplot. According to Ebdon & Gauch (2002), G6 was widely accepted to all environments with high seed yield performance (Fig. 1).

According to Kepton (1984), the distributions of genotypes or environment along the abscissa depict differences in main (additive) effects, whereas distributions along the ordinate indicate differences in interaction effects. He also suggested that genotypes which together form a group show similar adaptation, on the other hand environments which form a group together influences the genotypes in the same way. In the current study, the most of the genotypes dispersed along the abscissa indicating differences in main (additive) effects. The results of AMMI model analysis of variance also showed highest attribution of genotypes (83.95%) followed by GE interaction (12.02%) and the lowest attribution of environments towards total sum of square (Fig. 1). Variations in seed yield of linseed due to variation of genotypes, environments and GE interaction have also been reported by Tadesse et al. (2017), Adane & Ararsa (2018) and Amasalu (2020) in linseed, Memon et al. (2023) in castor and Daemo & Ashango (2024) in potato.

The IPCA scores of a genotype in the AMMI analysis are an indication of the adaptability over tested environments. The greater the IPCA1 scores (negative or positive) the more specific adaptive is genotypes to a particular environment. The more the IPCA scores close to zero, the more stable or adapted the genotypes are over all the environments tested (Aboye et al., 2021). Accordingly, G6 located most close to the IPCA line followed by G7 and G9, indicated that these 3 genotypes were widely accepted to all environments but seed yield of G1 was a little above the mean and that of G3 and G7 was below the overall mean. The rest 7 genotypes were scattered away from the origin indicating their specific adaptation to certain environments. Environments E10 was located on the origin and E2 & E6 near the origin of IPCA line with short vectors suggesting the least changeable environments; while E4 had the longest vector, which indicated the most changeable environments. The findings are in agreements with the reports of many other investigators (Cross et al. 1990, Edon and Gauch 2002, Adane & Ararsa 2018, Amasalu 2020 and Memon et al. 2023).

Genotypes which are grouped together had similar adaptation, while environments which are grouped together influence genotypes in similar ways. When a genotype and environment have the similar sign (negative or positive) on IPCA1 axis, their interaction is positive and this genotype is well adapted to this environment. But if they have opposite sign of IPCA1 scores, their interaction is negative and the environment is not suitable to this genotype as reported by Crossa et al. (1990). In the current study, all genotypes were scattered in the biplot field indicating wide variations in their adaptability.

In the AMMI 1 biplot (Fig. 1) showed that 9 environments forms a group above IPCA origin line and 3 of them forms another group below the IPCA line with short vectors, which indicated that each of two groups influenced the genotypes in similar ways. The IPCA1 scores of genotypes G1, G3 and G5, and environments E4 and E1 had the same (positive) sign and other 7 genotypes and 10 environments also had the same (negative) sign (Fig. 2). Therefore, interaction of genotypes with respective environments was positive. AMMI 1 biplot showed that the highest yielder genotype was G2 followed by G6, G1 and G4. The lowest yielding genotype was G9 followed by G10, G5 and G3. The most stable genotype was

G2 followed by G7, G9, G1 and G4, which were widely accepted to almost all environments. The most unstable genotype was G5 followed by G10. Among the environment E9, E5, E1 and E7 were most favorable environments for higher yield. Environments E10 was located on the origin whereas E2 & E6 located near the origin of IPCA line indicating the least changeable environments, while E4 had the longest vector, which indicated that it was the most changeable environments. Nine out of 12 environments were closely correlated and formed a group and influenced genotypes in similar way. The findings are in agreement with (Cross et al. 1990, Edon and Gauch 2002, Adane & Ararsa 2018, Amasalu 2020 and Memon et al. 2023).

AMMI 2 Biplot

AMMI model ANOVA (Table 3) revealed that the IPCA1 & IPCA2 together explained majority of variance (82.30%) where contribution of IPCA1 was 67.60% and that of IPCA2 was 14.70%. According to Yan (2011), Adane & Ararsa (2018) and Memon et al. (2023), an AMMI 2 biplot was created using IPCA1 and IPCA2 scores of genotypes as well as environments respectively on X-axis and Y-axis (Fig. 3). The biplot is an effective tool to explain the interaction of genotype with environment successfully in a multi-environmental trial. Vertical distance from a genotype to an environment vector depicted the degree of interaction with the specific environment (Yan 2011, Adane & Ararsa 2018 and Memon et al. 2023). A polygon view was created by connecting the vertex genotype markers with broken lines in all directions so that all genotypes were enclosed within the polygon. The lines connecting the vertex genotypes in the biplot polygon view indicates maximum seed yield in a certain environment (Memon et al. 2023). A set of 5 straight lines (dotted line) were drawn from the origin of the biplot to intersect each of the polygon side at right angle which divided the biplot into 5 sectors in the biplot plane containing genotypes and environments. It was found that the 12 test environments were distributed into 4 sections out of 5. Environments, E4, E3 & E11 placed in the sector 1 where the vertex genotype was G5 indicating its highest yield performance at E4 followed by E3 and E11. Two environments E2 & E10 located within sector 2, where the vertex genotype was G8 which performed best at these two environments. Genotype G2 was the vertex genotype within sector 3 where no environment was placed indicating its excellent performance at any or all of environments. Maximum of 6 environments, E5, E6, E7, E8, E9 & E12 were located within sector 4 and its vertex genotype was G10, which indicated that G10 performed best at these 6 environments. G4 was also a member of the sector 4 along with these 6 environments indicating its very well performance at these 6 environments. Another genotype G6 placed close to the biplot origin within sector 4 along with these environments indicating its excellent performance at all genotypes. The vector of E6 was the shortest placed near the origin indicating its less interaction with the genotypes. Sector 5 contained only one environment (E1) and two genotypes (G1 & G3). G1 was the vertex genotypes giving higher yield at E1 than G3 which was also a good performer at E1 (Fig. 2). at any or all of environments. Maximum of 6 environments, E5, E6, E7, E8, E9 & E12 were located within sector 4 and its vertex genotype was G10, which indicated that G10 performed best at these 6 environments. G4 was also a member of the sector 4 along with these 6 environments indicating its very well performance at these 6 environments. Another genotype G6 placed close to the biplot origin within sector 4 along with these environments indicating its excellent performance at all genotypes. The vector of E6 was the shortest placed near the origin indicating its less interaction with the genotypes. Sector 5 contained only one environment (E1) and two genotypes (G1 & G3). G1 was the vertex genotypes giving higher yield at E1 than G3 which was also a good performer at E1 (Fig. 2).

Figure 2. AMMI 2 Biplot of IPCA 1 Versus IPCA 2 of 10 Genotypes Tested across 12 Environments
Note: Abbreviation as in Table 1

The findings of the present study regarding relationship of genotypes with environments, and adaptability of linseed genotypes across 12 environments are in agreements with the reports of Temesgen et al. (2014) and Adane & Arasa (2018) in linseed and Memon et al. (2023) in castor.

GGE Biplot Analysis

The GGE biplot is an important visualization tool which illustrates which-won-where pattern and is useful for evaluation of genotypes and test environments. The polygon view of GGE biplot is an effective approach to identify best performing genotypes for a particular environment through visual observation of the interaction patterns between genotypes and environments in a multi-environmental trial data analysis (Yan and Kang 2003, 2007).

In the present study, the partitioning of GGE using GGE biplot analysis for 10 genotypes at 12 environments depicted that PCA1 and PCA2 accounted for respectively 88.80% and 7.70% of GGE sum of squares for seed yield. The two PCs together explained majority (96.508%) of total variation (Figure 3). A biplot was developed using PC1 on X-axis and PC2 on Y-axis. A polygon was formed by connecting the vertex genotypes with broken lines in the biplot. The polygon was subdivided into 6 separate sectors by vectors (dotted lines) that originated from origin of the biplot and extended to its side lines of with right angles. The GGE biplot revealed that all genotypes were dispersed into all 6 sections but tested environments fell into sections 1, 3 & 4.

In the present investigation, one environment, E4 fell in sector 1 with the vertex genotype G5 indicating that it was a high-yielding genotype for E4 following G3. Section-3 contained three environments, E1, E3 & E11 with vertex genotype G6, which was a high-yielding genotype for these three environments. Sector 4 contained most of the environments E2, E5, E6, E7, E8, E9, E10 & E12 with vertex genotype G2 which was the highest yielder at all of the 8 environments. G4 was also a member of the sector 4 and well performed at these 8 environments. G2 and G4 might be noted as mega-genotypes having yield

ability at most of the environments. G1, G9 and G10 were also vertex genotypes in sectors 2, 5 and 6, respectively; however, no environment fell in their sectors which suggested that these genotypes were low yielding genotypes at some or all sites. The results of the present investigation were comparable to the findings of Adane & Araarsa (2018) in linseed, Akter et al. (2015) in rice and Sakhare et al. (2018) in castor.

Figure 3. “Which-Won-Where” Pattern of GGE Biplot Polygon View Displaying the Genotype Main Effect plus $G \times E$ Interaction Effect of 10 Linseed Genotypes in Three Seasons Four Locations for Seed Yield per Hectare
Note: Abbreviation as in Table 1

According to the findings of Yan & Tinker (2006), the vertex genotypes were the most responsive genotypes, as they have the longest distance from the origin in their direction. Akter et al. (2015) opined that genotype which is located near the origin of a GGE biplot is less responsive compared to the vertex genotypes and stable in nature. Accordingly, G7 was located apparently near the biplot origin showed moderately average yield performance and it was less responsive to environments than the vertex genotypes. Genotypes around the origin of biplot were best suited to low yielding conditions because they are stable in nature. The GGE biplot view validated the findings presented in the AMMI 2 biplot. These findings are consistent with those made by Nzube et al. (2013) for maize hybrids. Similarly, Sakhare et al. (2018) carried out GGE biplot analysis for castor hybrids and extracted Aruna, 48-1, AKC 1, DCH 177 and DCS 9 as a poor yielder for seed yield.

Relationships among Test Environments

Another GGE biplot plot was created using PCA1 & PCA2 scores of 12 enrolments on X-axis and Y-axis respectively to depict relationship among the environments. A vector, represented by the line was drawn from origin of the biplot to the markers of genotypes. The angle between two environment vectors is related to the correlation coefficient between them. The cosine of the angles between vectors of environments depicts relationships between test environments. The acute angles indicate a strong positive

correlation, obtuse angles strong negative correlation or cross over GEI of genotypes, and right angle indicates no correlation (Yan & Tinker 2006). A short vector may indicate that the test environment is not related to other environments (Yan, 2002). Environments E1, E3 and E11 were grouped in quadrant II and the angles formed by these vectors were less than 90° which depicted strong correlations among these 3 environments. Seven of the 12 environments, namely E2, E5, E6, E7, E8, E9 and E12 were grouped together in the quadrant III indicating their positive and strong correlation among each other because all angles among vectors were less than 90° . Quadrant I contained only one environment (E4) and quadrant IV contained another one environment (E10). The two environment vectors formed an acute angle expressing strong correlation between two environments. A presence of close positive associations between these testing environments is an indication that similar information could be obtained about the genotypes from a fewer test environment and that is considered as an opportunity to reduce costs of germplasm evaluation when resources are scanty (Yan & Tinker 2006). The longer the environment vectors the more discrimination among the test genotypes. The longest vector was formed in E4 followed by E7, E9, E5 and E8.

Heat Map

The results depicted in AMMI 2 biplot and GGE biplot was comparable to the results illustrated in a heat map. A heat map was drawn based on seed yield to visualize adaptability of 10 genotypes across 12 environments, which depicted similar performance of the genotypes across 12 environments as observed in AMMI 2 biplot. The heat map depicted general adaption in all environments for genotypes G6 and G2 (except E4) with high yield (more than 1250 kg ha^{-1}). Generalized adaption in different environments was also shown by G3, G9 and G10 but seed yield was low (less than 1000 kg ha^{-1}). The best environment was E4 for G1 and G5 with high yield (more than 1250 kg ha^{-1}). G3 and G8 had generalized adaption with medium yield. According to the heat map, genotypes G2 and G6 showed a universally superior performance across all environments followed by G2. Of these 3, G6 showed consistently higher yield at all environments and G2 at eleven of the twelve environments. Although G3, G9 & G10 are also performed uniformly in all environment seed yield was lower compared to G2 and G6 (Fig. 4). The heat map validates the relationships of genotypes with environments (Fig. 5). The relationship of the 10 genotypes with 12 environments tested recorded from AMMI biplots and GGE biplots have been validate by the heat map (Figs. 2, 3 & 4)

Figure 4. Vector View of GGE Biplot for 12 Environments (E)

Figure 5. Heat Map Showing Adaptability of Ten Linseed Genotypes in 12 Different Environments and Their Seed Yielding Capability

Note: Abbreviation as in Table 1

AMMI Stability Analysis

A quantitative stability measure is required for quantifying and ranking genotypes based on their yield stability measure but the AMMI model does not make such provision. Therefore, AMMI stability parameters are used for the purposes. Six stability statistics were computed (Table 5) using R software. The simple interpretation of the stability parameters is that a genotype with lower score value is considered to be more stable (Aboye, 2021).

According to the ASV stability statistic, G6, G9 and G1 were the most stable but G5, G10 and G8 genotypes were unstable genotypes for seed yield in the tested environments. According to SIPC, the most stable genotypes were G9, G6 and G7, whereas G5, G2 and G8 were the most unstable genotypes for seed yield. Based on EV value the most stable genotype for seed yield were G6 followed by G9 and G4. On the other hand, G5, G2 and G4 were unstable genotypes. The CV score for seed yield revealed that G6, G9 and G6 were the most stable but G5 and G10 were unstable genotypes. Considering these stability statistics, G2 might be noted as the best performing genotypes followed by G6 and G4. The findings of the present investigation are in agreement with findings of Aboye (2021), who also worked with linseed genotypes.

Table 5. Values of AMMI Stability Parameters for Eight Linseed Genotypes Tasted at 12 Environments

Genotype		Yield (kg ha^{-1})	ASV	SIPC	EV	CV (%)	WAASB
Code	Name						
G1	Neela (G1)	1149 (4)	25.3 (4)	29.18 (4)	0.122 (5)	7.99 (5)	5.03 (4)
G2	BD-10708	1346 (1)	47.1 (5)	34.72 (9)	0.145 (9)	8.05 (6)	8.09 (9)
G3	BD-10707	853 (7)	32.64 (7)	26.62 (6)	0.106 (6)	9.80 (7)	5.86 (6)
G4	Lin-1403	1151 (3)	34.1 (6)	22.41 (5)	0.056 (3)	6.21 (3)	5.78 (5)
G5	Lin-2403	830 (8)	89.2 (10)	33.85 (10)	0.139(10)	20.42 (10)	13.47 (10)

G6	BD-10698	1285 (2)	4.6 (2)	8.39 (1)	0.013 (1)	3.61 (1)	1.16 (2)
G7	Lin-S-19	1070 (5)	15.2 (3)	29.85 (3)	0.140 (4)	7.20 (4)	3.92 (3)
G8	Lin-1503/2	907 (6)	36.4 (8)	35.46 (8)	0.138 (8)	10.39 (6)	7.38 (8)
G9	Lin-1203	625 (10)	1.9 (1)	10.15 (2)	0.023 (2)	4.87 (2)	0.88 (1)
G10	Lin-W-17	786 (9)	41.2 (9)	30.12 (7)	0.119 (7)	12.59 (9)	7.25 (7)

ASV=AMMI stability value, SIPC = Sum of IPCs, EV = Eigenvalue stability parameter, CV = Coefficient of variation.,
 Figures within parentheses indicate ranking values.

Y x WAASB Biplot Analysis

The values of six stability statistics was not consistent with the genotypes and created a mystification. To avoid such confusion, the WAASB (Weighted Average of Absolute Scores from the singular value decomposition of the matrix of BLUPs for the GEI effects generated by an LMM) was developed to study GEI through biplots and to select stable genotypes (Olivoto & Lucio 2019). Y x WAASB biplot was developed using seed yield on the X-axis and WAASB values on the Y-axis. The tested genotypes and/or environments (years/season) are distributed in the biplot into four quadrants, facilitating visual simultaneous selection of genotype with high seed yield and stability. The general interpretations are that the environments or genotypes located in quadrant I are noted as unstable with low yield (below the grand mean); those in quadrant II are high yielder (above the grand mean) but unstable; those in quadrant III have low productivity but stable; and those in quadrant IV are highly productive and broadly adapted due to the high magnitude of the response variable and high stability performance (Vineeth et al. 2021).

Figure 5. Seed Yield (kg ha⁻¹) per Plant vs WAASB Biplot Based on Combined Interpretation of Productivity (SY) and Stability (WAASB) for 11seed Genotypes Evaluated across 12 Environments during Rabi 2020-23
 Note: Abbreviation as in Table 1

In the present investigation, genotypes G3, G10, G8 and G5 fell in quadrant 1 of the Y x WAASB biplot (Figs. 6), which indicated poorest productivity as well as stability of the genotypes. Two genotypes, G2 & G4 along with environments E3 & E4 located in quadrant 2 indicating poor stability but higher seed yield. Four environments, E2, E6, E8 & E10, and a genotype, G9 were located in the quadrant 3. The G9 depicted the highest stability (due to the lowest WAAS value) but the lowest seed yield. The remaining 5 environments (E8, E6, E2, E11 & E3, and 3 genotypes (G1, G6 and G7) were found in the quadrant 4 having higher stability with higher seed yield. Considering their tremendous stability along with excellent seed yielding G6 and G1 were noted as the most promising genotypes and may be selected for cultivation. The findings supported the findings of Aboye (2021), Vineeth et al. (2021) and Memon et al. (2023).

Conclusion

Results of the current study revealed that linseed seed yield was responsible to genetic variability of linseed genotypes (G), remarkable variation of the growing environments (E) and the G × E interaction effects. However, contribution of genotypes towards yield variation was almost seven times higher than that of the environment. The AMMI model ANOVA revealed that main effects of genotypes, environments and their interaction explained 83.95%, 1.07% and 12.02% of seed yield variation, respectively. The GE interaction was further subdivided into 9 IPCAs of which the first 6 were significant, and the first two IPCAs explained 82.3% of total sum of square where IPCA1 explained 67.60% and IPCA 2 14.70%. Mean comparison showed that mean seed yield of ten genotypes varied from 625 to 1345 kg ha⁻¹ and that of 12 environments varied from 937-1050 kg h⁻¹ with a grand mean of 1000 kg ha⁻¹. AMMI 1, AMMI 2 and GGE biplot analyses depicted that the highest yielder genotype was G2 followed by G6, G1 and G4. The lowest yielding genotype was G9 followed by G10, G5 and G3. The most stable genotype was G2 followed by G7, G9, G1 and G4, which were widely accepted to almost all environments. The most unstable genotype was G5 followed by G10. Y x WAASB biplot analysis and heat map illustration validated the findings about yield performance and stability of genotypes. The ASV, EV, CV, SIPC and yield index analyses revealed that genotypes G2, G4 and G6 were found to be superior genotypes in seed yield and consistently demonstrating high mean performance across tested environments. Considering the results of biplot analyses and stability parameters like ASV, SIPC, CV, and EV, genotypes G1, G2, G4 and G6 were identified as superior genotypes. The genotypes, G6 exhibited high seed yield, wide adaptation and excellent stable performance over all four tested locations. Thus BD-10698 (G6) can be selected as a variety for cultivation in the saline affected soils of South-Western coastal region of Bangladesh. Genotypes BD-10708 (G2) and Lin-1403 (G4) showed excellent yield performance but medium stability, while Lin-1203 (G9) showed excellent stability but low yield performance. So, BD-10707, Lin-1403 and Lin-1203 can be utilized to develop salt tolerant linseed variety through required breeding program.

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